

Aerodynamic Optimization of the TurboLab Stator: A Comparative Study between Conventional and Adjoint-based Approaches

Ilias Vasilopoulos*, Peter Flassig and Marcus Meyer
Rolls-Royce Deutschland Ltd & Co KG, Blankenfelde-Mahlow, D-15827, Germany

Kyra Reiche
Brandenburg University of Technology, Cottbus, D-03048, Germany

The goal of this work is to develop a CAD-based aerodynamic optimization workflow for the application on the TU Berlin TurboLab Stator benchmark. Two different approaches are examined and compared: (i) A conventional gradient-free optimization procedure which makes use of 2D and 3D CFD results and constructs a response surface to obtain the optimum solution and (ii) an adjoint gradient-based optimization process, where the adjoint derivatives w.r.t. the design parameters are calculated by linking the adjoint surface sensitivity map with the model's geometric sensitivities. The latter are computed using finite-differences between discrete representations of the CAD geometries. Both methods are applied to the turbomachinery test case, where two objective functions and three operating points are considered. Moreover, manufacturing constraints have to be incorporated in the process chain, which makes the case even more challenging. Since the optimization output is already in CAD format, there is no requirement for a back-to-CAD step and the optimum blade can be straightforwardly manufactured.

I. Introduction

For turbomachinery applications, adjoint-driven CFD design offers an efficient approach to improve the aerodynamic performance of the engine gas path and its components, like rotor and stator blades¹. Especially for high ratios between number of design parameters such as blade chord length or blade's thicknesses and number of aerodynamic design criteria such as efficiency, total pressure ratio or capacity, adjoint-based numerical optimization shows clear benefits against classical search strategies in terms of computational effort, which becomes independent of the number of design parameters. This has been demonstrated by a number of publications, such as Ref. 2-4. Nevertheless, the adjoint method has to be robust and stable for realistic flow characteristics, such as flow separation or instabilities in wakes and vortices⁵. Furthermore, challenges related to the industrial applicability of adjoint-based methods are not sufficiently resolved yet.

Adjoint-based optimization strategies can easily manipulate a CAD-free parameterization (such as an FFD control box) or even use all the model's surface mesh node coordinates as design variables, which represents the richest design space the CFD can evaluate. However, a major drawback of such CAD-free methods is that they result in an optimized mesh, which then has to be converted back to CAD in order to obtain the optimized geometry for further analysis or manufacturing. This mesh-to-CAD step is a non-trivial task and it may require extensive user intervention. Moreover, geometric constraints are best incorporated within a CAD framework and their imposition can be a priori guaranteed through the parameterization of the CAD model. Thus, recent research has been focused on how to include the CAD system into the design loop and some promising approaches are currently under investigation within the EC ITN IODA project⁶.

For a CAD-centric approach it is of great importance to have universal and robust methods in place to link the adjoint-based CFD results directly to existing and approved design parameterizations^{7,8}. This enables both error-free mapping of the adjoint gradient results to CAD and fast and explicit assessment of design parameter sensitivities by the design engineers. In order to perform gradient-based optimization using a CAD-based parameterization, the sensitivities of the model's boundary w.r.t. the design parameters have to be computed. Differentiating the underlying parameterization of the CAD software to obtain these geometric sensitivities is usually not an option within an industrial environment, where closed-source commercial CAD tools (such as

* Corresponding author, ilias.vasilopoulos@rolls-royce.com.

Siemens NX or CATIA V5) are widely used. In this work, the geometric sensitivities are calculated using finite-differences (FD) between discrete representations (surface meshes) of the CAD geometries. The meshes are generated in PADRAM⁹, the Rolls-Royce in-house meshing tool, which can maintain the mesh topology. An alternative would be to use the design velocity approach, as presented in Ref. 10.

Although gradient-based optimization techniques can efficiently find local minima, their main drawback is that they do not guarantee to return a global optimum solution. On the other hand, global optimizers such as evolutionary algorithms can find global minima, but require large numbers of function evaluations, especially in high-dimensional design spaces. However, surrogate-based optimization approaches can manage this “curse of dimensionality” by building an inexpensive response surface approximation^{11,12}. A set of initial high-fidelity CFD evaluations is used as training data for the construction of the approximation function, which will replace the computationally expensive model throughout the optimization. Such a conventional approach is also employed in this work and the optimization results are compared with the adjoint-based ones. In general, hybrid methods which first use a surrogate model for design space exploration and then employ a gradient-based technique to reach the optimum are becoming more and more of interest to the research community.

This paper summarizes the activities which have been conducted in an industrial environment for the third test case from the “AboutFlow CFD Optimisation Benchmark”. Aim of the test case is to optimize the 3D shape of the TurboLab Stator from the Technical University of Berlin with respect to aerodynamic criteria. Specifically, the TurboLab Stator is a compressor stator in a rig setup with subsonic flow but high degree of turning¹³.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Sec. II presents the TU Berlin TurboLab Stator benchmark test case and the corresponding optimization requirements. Sec. III contains the baseline blade analysis, while the selected parameterization is described in Sec. IV. The optimization results obtained from the conventional and the adjoint-based approach are presented in Sec. V and VI, respectively, followed by the conclusions in Sec. VII.

II. Test Case Description

The TurboLab Stator is a compressor stator designed at the Chair for Aero Engines of the TU Berlin, Germany. The design of its blades was based on a representative stator geometry, as used in modern jet engine compressors. The initial geometry of the blades is shown in Fig. 1.

The goal is to optimize this baseline blade w.r.t. the total pressure loss over a prescribed incidence range, while turning the incoming swirling flow of 42° whirl angle into an axial flow. A detailed description of the CFD domain, flow boundary conditions, optimization requirements and manufacturing constraints can be found in Ref. 13. The CAD model of the CFD domain is also provided and is available in various formats (iges, STEP, parasolid).

Figure 1. Initial stator blade geometry.

A. Optimization Requirements

Two optimization criteria are considered leading to a multi-objective optimization problem. The first objective to be minimized is the total pressure loss between CFD inlet and CFD outlet, defined as the total pressure difference (between inlet and outlet) divided by the inlet dynamic pressure. In this work mass averaged values over the inlet and outlet have been used. The second objective to be minimized is the flow angle deviation from the axial direction at the CFD outlet, which is defined as the integral from hub to casing of the exit whirl angle squared. This objective has been implemented here as a mass averaging over the outlet of the whirl angle squared.

In order for the optimization output to be robust against variations of the inlet whirl angle, a multi-point optimization problem is defined. The inlet whirl angle is allowed to vary by $\pm 5^\circ$, thus two off-design operating points are considered (OD+ and OD-) with an inlet whirl angle of 47° and 37° , respectively. The prescribed weights for the different operating conditions to be considered by the optimization technique are 50% for the design point (DP) and 25% for the OD points.

Finally, there is a flow constraint requirement to keep the mass flow of the full annulus at 9.0 ± 0.1 kg/s over the whole aforementioned operating range.

B. Manufacturing Constraints

The following manufacturing constraints have to be taken into account during the optimization process:

- 1) The number of blades is fixed and equal to 15.
- 2) The axial chord length of the blade has to be kept constant.

- 3) The minimum value for leading and trailing edge circle radius is 1 mm.
- 4) Two screws of 2.5 mm radius and 20 mm depth have to fit inside the blade at both hub and casing. Thus, the blade thickness at these positions has to accommodate a cylinder of material with a radius of 5 mm and a depth of 20 mm, as shown in Fig. 2. The two holes can be placed arbitrarily inside the profile shape, but have to be at least 60 mm apart from each other.
- 5) The blade has to be mountable on a plate of 200 mm x 80 mm as part of the cylindrical casing.
- 6) Hub endwall contouring is allowed, although the change in radius must be between -5 mm and 10 mm.

Figure 2. Profile shape of baseline blade and manufacturing constraints specification.

III. Baseline Blade Analysis

The baseline stator geometry has been re-parameterized (as described in Sec. IV) using Parablading¹⁴, the Rolls-Royce in-house turbomachinery parameterization software. This is a blade geometry generation tool for describing 3D blade shapes on the basis of radially stacked 2D blade sections. The re-parameterization resulted in a slightly modified baseline geometry, which is of minor importance since it does not affect the optimization result.

Figure 3 shows the block-structured 1.9 million node hexahedral mesh that was generated in PADRAM, after conducting a mesh refinement study to achieve a mesh-independent prediction of the objective functions. The maximum first node y^+ value is below 4, which is acceptable when using the wall function technique in the CFD simulation.

Figure 3. Stator CFD mesh generated in PADRAM.

A steady RANS compressible flow solver with Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model and its corresponding discrete adjoint solver were used for computing the flow and sensitivity map, respectively. These are part of the Rolls-Royce in-house HYDRA¹⁵ suite of codes, which have been extensively validated and applied to various industrial cases^{9,16}. More details regarding the underlying theory and implemented algorithm can be found in Ref. 17,18. The nonlinear flow solver uses a node-based finite-volume discretization method and the pseudo-time-marching to steady state is accelerated by a block-Jacobi preconditioner and a geometric multigrid technique.

A. Primal Analysis

Three primal/flow CFD simulations have been performed (one per operating point). The mass flow constraint is satisfied by adjusting the outlet static pressure during the iterative solution, until the prescribed mass flow is achieved. In 1500 iterations the RMS residual drops between 7 and 8 orders of magnitude for all three operating points and the flow is considered converged since the values of both objective functions change only negligibly.

Figure 4 illustrates the close-to-surface streamlines for the DP simulation. It can be seen that there is a corner flow separation occurring on both hub and tip, which then expands along the suction side of the blade. This is common for highly loaded compressor stators and it has been experimentally observed in Ref. 19. The situation is similar also for the OD- and OD+ points, where the separation areas move towards the trailing and leading edge, respectively. In order to decrease the stator total pressure loss, these separation areas have to be reduced.

Figure 4. Baseline blade streamlines.

The DP total pressure distribution at an axial cross-section close to the trailing edge is shown in Fig. 5. The lowest values appear at the areas of separated flow. After converging the flow CFD simulations, the total pressure loss (P_{loss}) objective was computed for DP, OD- and OD+, resulting in 7.64%, 7.56% and 8.53%, respectively. This leads to a weighted P_{loss} of 7.85% for the baseline stator blade.

Figure 5. Baseline total pressure distribution.

Figure 6. Baseline exit whirl angle distribution.

Finally, Fig. 6 shows the DP axial whirl angle distribution at the outlet of the CFD domain. It is noticed that the outlet whirl angle highly deviates from zero, which means that the baseline stator blade does not achieve the prescribed 42° flow turning. The exit flow angle deviation (α_E^2) objective (as defined in Sec. II) has been calculated for DP, OD- and OD+ conditions, resulting in 12.18, 9.29 and 17.85 deg^2 , respectively. Thus, the weighted α_E^2 for the baseline stator blade is 12.88 deg^2 .

The weighted P_{loss} and α_E^2 are the two contradicting objectives w.r.t. which the stator should be optimized.

B. Adjoint Analysis

Given that two objective functions are considered for each operating point, six adjoint CFD simulations need to be performed in total. This cannot be avoided since each operating point has a different flow solution, with which the adjoint problem is started. In 1000 iterations the adjoint residual drops around 4 orders of magnitude for all the simulations and the adjoint flow is considered converged. This was proven to be adequate to compute flow sensitivities leading to relatively accurate gradient information, after a FD validation study has been conducted.

The adjoint solver provides the volume sensitivities (i.e. the change in objective function w.r.t. a volume mesh node perturbation). The surface sensitivities (i.e. the change in objective function w.r.t. a surface mesh node perturbation) are obtained using the inverse operation of a spring-based mesh deformation algorithm on the volume sensitivities. Finally, the adjoint surface sensitivity map is derived by projecting each surface node's sensitivity vector onto its corresponding boundary normal. The DP sensitivity maps for P_{loss} and α_E^2 objectives are illustrated in Fig. 7 and 8, respectively.

Figure 7 shows that the P_{loss} objective is more sensitive to suction side perturbations, especially close to the leading edge, where highly sensitive stripes appear. Moreover, the sensitivity map captures the previously mentioned separation areas, which need to be modified in order to reduce P_{loss} . According to Fig. 8, the α_E^2 objective can be decreased by perturbing the area close to the trailing edge, which will aim to achieve an axial flow at the stator exit. The sensitivity maps at the OD points have trends similar to these.

Figure 7. Suction side of baseline blade colored by DP sensitivity map w.r.t. P_{loss} objective.

Figure 8. Pressure side of baseline blade colored by DP sensitivity map w.r.t. α_E^2 objective.

IV. Blade Parameterization

The geometry of the stator aerofoil is defined by a set of individual 2D profiles from hub to tip. Using a curve in the radial direction defined by axial and circumferential shifts, the design sections are stacked from the hub to the casing, resulting to the final 3D aerofoil shape^{7,20,21}. This can be easily exported to a CAD software without any loss of information. For each profile contour definition the classical section build-up is applied²², which is originally based on the superposition of a camber-line $f(x)$ and a thickness distribution $T(x)$. However, instead of using the camber-line, the camber-line angle distribution $\beta(x)$ is preferred. For specific reasons⁸, such as better comparison of different designs, it is common practise to normalise both distributions using the blade inlet and exit angles (β_I and β_E), as well as the chord length c . The non-dimensional distributions are defined as

$$\tilde{\beta}(\tilde{x}) = \frac{\beta_I - \beta(\tilde{x})}{\beta_I - \beta_E} \in [0,1], \quad \tilde{x} = \frac{x}{c} \in [0,1] \quad (1)$$

$$\tilde{T}(\tilde{x}) = \begin{cases} \frac{T(\tilde{x}) - T_I}{T_{max} - T_I} & \text{for } 0 \leq \tilde{x} \leq \tilde{p}, \\ \frac{T(\tilde{x}) - T_E}{T_{max} - T_E} & \text{for } \tilde{p} < \tilde{x} \leq 1 \end{cases} \in [0,1] \quad (2)$$

where $\tilde{p} = p/c \in [0,1]$ is the normalized position of maximum thickness for the non-dimensional thickness distribution, as illustrated in Fig. 9. In this work, the normalized distributions are parameterized by B-splines²³ using 7 control points (CP) for the non-dimensional camber-line angle distribution and 9 CP for the normalized thickness distribution, as shown in Fig. 10. For the latter distribution 3 degrees of freedom are fixed in order to satisfy a geometric constraint at the position of maximum thickness.

Figure 9. Parameterization of blade section: (a) Profile skeleton, (b) camber-line angle and thickness distributions, and (c) non-dimensional distributions.

A common number of design sections is 7. Thus, the potential design space dimension amounts to 196: 5 discrete design parameters (r_I , r_E , β_I , β_E and T_{max}), 10 CP parameters for the non-dimensional camber-line angle distribution, 11 CP parameters for the non-dimensional thickness distribution and 2 stacking parameters for the axial and circumferential shift (per section). However, the stacking shifts at hub and tip are kept constant, leading to a design space of 192 parameters which were used by the adjoint-based optimization.

Figure 10. B-spline curves with arrows indicating CP perturbations for normalized camber-line angle (a) and thickness (b) distributions.

On the other hand, the design space dimension is reduced for the conventional design strategy in order to decrease the computational cost of the method. From an industrial point of view, 192 design parameters are too many to be managed by zero order techniques in an acceptable timeframe. Hence, only 3 design sections are used in this case. Additionally, the leading edge and trailing edge radii are kept constant during the optimization and the number of B-spline CP for distributions (1) and (2) is reduced to 4 and 7, respectively. For the stacking line only 2 axial and 2 circumferential shifts are used at constant radial heights and the complete curve is obtained by cubic-spline interpolation. Table 1 summarizes and compares the design spaces explored by the two different optimization approaches.

Table 1. Design space information for the conventional and the adjoint-based optimization.

Discrete design parameter	Conventional Optimization	Adjoint-based Optimization
Leading edge radius (r_l)	Not used	Used
Trailing edge radius (r_E)	Not used	Used
Blade inlet angle (β_l)	Used	Used
Blade exit angle (β_E)	Used	Used
Maximum thickness (T_{max})	Used	Used
Normalized camber-line angle curve	B-Spline with 4 CP	B-Spline with 7 CP (Fig. 10a)
Normalized thickness curve	B-Spline with 7 CP	B-Spline with 9 CP (Fig. 10b)
No. of design parameters per section	3+4+7=14	5+10+11=26
No. of design sections	3	7
Span-wise position of design sections	20, 50, 80 (%)	0, 15, 30, 50, 70, 85, 100 (%)
Axial shifts	Two at 30, 70 (% of span)	Five at 15, 30, 50, 70, 85 (% of span)
Circumferential shifts	Two at 30, 70 (% of span)	Five at 15, 30, 50, 70, 85 (% of span)
Total No. of design parameters	14*3+4=46	26*7+10=192
Elliptical leading edge	Applied for optimum blade	Applied for optimum blade

In order to increase the performance of numerical optimization algorithms, implicit geometric constraints such as smoothness requirements for the non-dimensional distributions and proper design space bounds should be fulfilled and defined, respectively, a priori. Therefore, the B-spline CP coordinates are not taken directly, but relative to artificial normalized design parameters p_i which are varied by the optimization algorithm, as explained in Ref. 24. Moreover, it is empirically well known that optimal compressor blade sections with subsonic flow are characterized by inflection point free non-dimensional camber-line angle and thickness distributions. As a result, the mapping of Ref. 24 between CP coordinates and design parameters is modified in such a way that inflection point free distributions are guaranteed a priori.

Finally, the parameterization within Parablading enables to maintain a CAD-based representation of the stator geometry during the optimization. This is achieved by fitting B-spline curves at the pressure and suction sides of the blade sections, which are used to create a NURBS²³ patch for each side. Thus, any stator aerofoil in Parablading can be exported as a set of NURBS patches written in a STEP file.

V. Conventional Gradient-free Optimization

Numerous strategies exist for optimizing the aerodynamic performance of an axial compressor blade without using gradients. A common practise in industry is to first find proper section geometries using 2D CFD evaluations and then continue with time consuming 3D CFD analyses to search for a suitable section stacking in the radial direction²⁰. According to this approach, the conventional gradient-free optimization is performed in two main steps: (i) Individual section optimizations using 2D CFD and (ii) emulation-based stacking

optimization based on 3D CFD results. However, an important intermediate step is included before the stacking optimization in order to maximise the design space of the stacking parameters, by simultaneously fulfilling the screw constraints of the test case presented in Sec. II.

A. Individual Section Optimizations

An individual single-objective optimization subject to aerodynamic constraints is performed for each design section. The minimization of the pressure loss coefficient as defined in Ref. 24 is sought and the blade-to-blade solver Mises²⁵ is used for the 2D flow prediction. The exit flow angle and the boundary-layer shape factor distribution are considered as constraints, to account for a proper flow turning and a stable off-design performance of the sections, respectively. Although the sections need to turn the flow to a zero angle, this constraint is adjusted for the 2D section optimization to also indirectly consider the 3D flow effects.

One section optimization using the Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy²⁶ (CMA-ES) with parallel design evaluation on one standard engineering PC takes approximately 30 minutes. Since only 3 sections are considered for the optimization, the geometry of the remaining sections is obtained using a cubic interpolation within Parablading. Figure 11 shows the radial distributions of the pressure loss coefficient and exit flow angle for both nominal and 2D optimized aerofoils. It can be seen that not only the optimized sections, but also the interpolated ones, have lower losses at design point conditions. Regarding the flow angle, all of the nominal aerofoil sections do less turning than required. On the other hand, the turning for the optimized sections changes from hub to tip according to the expected 3D flow behavior, i.e. from underturning at the hub towards overturning at the tip.

Figure 11. Aerodynamic Mises-based 2D performance of nominal (black) and 2D optimized (blue) aerofoils: Pressure loss coefficient (left) and exit flow angle (right) radial distributions.

B. Stacking Bounds Optimization

For the second step of the conventional aerofoil optimization, design space bounds for the axial and theta shifts need to be specified. From an aerodynamic perspective, a large design space is preferable to benefit as much as possible from the 3D shaping, i.e. to allow the formation of lean and sweep. However, the final aerofoil has to fulfil the manufacturing requirement to fit screws of specified length at both hub and casing, which highly depends on the 3D aerofoil shape. This means that the smaller the stacking modifications, the higher the probability to satisfy the constraints, but also the smaller the aerodynamic performance benefit. Therefore, the process outlined in Fig. 12 has been developed to maximize the bounds for the two axial and two theta shifts.

More specifically, the process tries to optimize for the two parameters s_1 and s_2 by maximizing their sum. One parameter defines the lower and upper bounds for the axial shifts, and the other one for the theta shifts, relative to user specified reference bounds. For this single-objective optimization problem the CMA-ES is used. A combination of the two parameters is feasible if the cumulated area violation A is less or equal to zero. To compute this cumulated area violation a set of differently stacked aerofoils is generated in Parablading and evaluated according to the screw constraints. The different stacking definitions are obtained running an optimal Latin Hypercube Sampling based on the current stacking bounds.

In order to check if the two screws can fit at the hub and tip, a simple algorithm has been scripted in Python. Basically, the algorithm takes two different sections and checks whether or not the two screw circles lie within both sections contours, as shown in Fig. 13. Only in the case where both circles are completely surrounded by both sections the area violation is set to zero, otherwise the design is penalized. According to the required depth of the holes, the sections at 0 and 30% of blade height are selected for the hub constraint, and the sections at 70 and 100% of blade height for the casing constraint. The two holes can be placed arbitrarily inside the profile

Figure 12. Optimization workflow to maximize the stacking bounds subject to a guaranteed manufacturability.

shape, but have to be at least 60 mm apart from each other. So, an internal optimization is performed within the script to determine the three coordinates x_1 , y_1 and Δx_2 (defining the holes positions according to Fig. 13), which provide a feasible solution if any, i.e. with zero area violation. Including this constraint into the stacking bounds definition results to the maximum allowable design space for the axial and theta shifts, where the manufacturing constraints are guaranteed a priori.

Figure 13. Check of screw constraints exemplarily shown for the hub of a feasible design.

C. Emulation-based Stacking Optimization

Using the stacking bounds found in the previous step for the two axial and two theta shifts, a set of 14 differently stacked blades is generated in Parablading. The radial distributions of the axial and theta shifts are derived using a cubic spline interpolation for the intermediate sections, while there are no shifts applied at the hub and tip. At this point, a DoE is run and all the blades are evaluated by the 3D CFD solver HYDRA for each of the three different operating conditions (CH=OD-, DP and ST=OD+). The objective functions of interest (P_{loss} and α_E^2) are obtained by the simulations as described in Sec. II. Additionally, the area violation at hub and tip is computed for all of the 14 blades according to the previous subsection.

Based on the obtained data from the 3D simulations, eight Gaussian process emulators are trained, i.e. three for the total pressure loss (P_{loss}) and three for the exit whirl angle objective (α_E^2) at DP, CH and ST conditions, plus two for the hub and tip area violation. The accuracy of the prediction from the emulators is proven to be high, since the resulting residuals from a leave-one-out cross validation study (illustrated in Fig. 14) were found to be relatively low.

Figure 14. Results of leave-one-out cross validations to evaluate the prediction quality of the trained Gaussian process emulators for the conventional stacking optimization.

Finally, an emulation-based multi-objective optimization is performed using the AMGA²⁷. The goal is to minimize both weighted $Ploss$ and α_E^2 objectives simultaneously by varying the 4 stacking parameters. For each design the screw constraints at hub and tip are checked as well, in order to guarantee feasible optimum solutions.

Figure 15 shows the objective space with all the feasible designs after one AMGA optimization. The aerofoils of the two corner points of the Pareto-front are also displayed in this figure. These blades were selected and re-evaluated running HYDRA, and the results were similar to the prediction of the emulators. For the blade of minimum weighted loss the objectives are $Ploss = 8.08\%$ and $\alpha_E^2 = 1.3 \text{ deg}^2$, and for the blade of minimum weighted exit flow angle $Ploss = 8.16\%$ and $\alpha_E^2 = 1.2 \text{ deg}^2$. Comparing with the values for the baseline blade presented in Sec. III, it can be concluded that the conventional gradient-free optimization approach managed to produce blades with highly decreased flow angle deviation, but failed to also decrease the total pressure loss.

Figure 15. Results of one emulation-based multi-objective optimization using the AMGA: Feasible objective space with non-dominated designs in blue (left), and aerofoil comparison in Parablading between the baseline geometry shown in blue and the two corner Pareto-optima shown in orange and green, respectively (right).

VI. Adjoint Gradient-based Optimization

Figure 16. Gradient-based optimization workflow using adjoint derivatives.

The automated gradient-based optimization workflow which was developed in this work is outlined in Fig. 16. The baseline geometry is exported from Parablading and imported into PADRAM, where the baseline CFD mesh is generated. The HYDRA primal solver reads in this mesh and performs in parallel the three flow simulations for the three different operating points. Then, the HYDRA adjoint solver reads in the converged flow solutions and executes in parallel the six adjoint simulations, which result in six sensitivity maps (dJ/dX_S).

While this process is running, a Python script is used to slightly perturb a design parameter inside Parablading, which leads to a slightly perturbed geometry. The perturbed geometry is then meshed using PADRAM and this inner loop is repeated for all of the design parameters. This step is essential in order to compute the geometric sensitivities ($dX_S/d\alpha$) using FD between the baseline mesh and each of the perturbed meshes. In general, this approach may be prohibitive for industrial test cases, since the computational cost scales with the number of design parameters, and it cannot cope with changes in mesh topology which occur during remeshing. However, in our case PADRAM can remesh the CFD domain within only 5 sec, while maintaining the mesh topology. Thus, the geometric sensitivities for all of the 192 design parameters considered for the optimization can be calculated in a serial manner within 90 min, which is negligible compared to the total cost of the primal and adjoint solutions.

Following the chain rule, the gradients of the objective functions w.r.t. the design parameters ($dJ/d\alpha$) are computed by taking the inner product of each sensitivity map with each geometric sensitivity field. As a result, 6 gradient vectors of 192 components are obtained. The weighted *Ploss* gradient is derived using the same weighted sum for the gradient vectors of the different operating points that was used for the objective function values. Similarly, the weighted α_E^2 gradient is computed. Then, this gradient information is passed to a steepest descent optimizer and it is used to update the design space and thus the baseline geometry.

The whole process is wrapped in Python and is repeated until the optimization criteria are met. Finally, it should be noted that the developed optimization workflow can run automatically in batch mode and does not require any user intervention.

A. Augmented Objective Optimization

A single-objective optimization problem was considered using the weighted sum approach. The two objectives are equally weighted, since they are of the same order of magnitude ($Ploss = 7.85$, $\alpha_E^2 = 12.88$), and an augmented objective function is defined as the sum: $F_{aug} = Ploss + \alpha_E^2$. As a result, the baseline value for F_{aug} is equal to 20.72. In order to be consistent, the gradient of F_{aug} w.r.t. the design parameters is also given by the sum of *Ploss* and α_E^2 gradients.

The F_{aug} value and its gradient are read in by the steepest descent optimizer, which will predict the optimum step-size η_{opt} using a line-search approach. More specifically, a function of η is defined as $h(\eta) = F_{aug}(\alpha_0 - \eta \nabla F_{aug})$ and its minimum w.r.t η is sought. A convex parabolic approximation is assumed for h and its analytical expression can be obtained by computing the coefficients of a 2nd order polynomial. This requires three pieces of information. The first two are $h(0)$ and $dh/d\eta(0)$, which can be straightforwardly derived from F_{aug} and ∇F_{aug} . For the third one, an initial step for $\eta = 1$ is done and the design vector is updated leading to an updated geometry, which is then meshed and evaluated using the flow solver. The new resulting F_{aug} is equal to $h(1)$. Finally, η_{opt} is analytically derived using the constructed polynomial expression. This line-search approach increases the computational cost of each design iteration by another primal analysis (3 flow simulations), which is however compensated by the resulting faster optimization convergence.

The optimization convergence is plotted in Fig. 17, where it can be seen that the optimum is found in only 5 design steps and F_{aug} (in grey) is decreased by 57.1%. This results from a large decrease in α_E^2 (in orange) by 93.4% and a small increase in $Ploss$ (in blue) by 2.4%. Increased total pressure loss is expected for the correct stator turning (axial flow at the exit), since the flow deflection is increased. As already mentioned, these two objectives are contradicting (the gradients point towards different directions at the optimum blade), meaning that the optimization output would be different for a different weighting of the objectives. Repeating the optimization for a number of different weights would lead to a set of non-dominated solutions in objective space, known as the Pareto-front. However, since the total computational cost of the optimization was around 90 hours on 60 CPU cores, this was not pursued.

Figure 17. Optimization convergence of augmented objective function and its components.

Throughout the optimization, all the manufacturing constraints have been satisfied by the parameterization approach in Parablading, except for the fixture holes constraint. A Python script was created in order to automatically check whether the holes fit inside the optimum blade. It turned out that the holes break the blade surface in the vicinity of the hub region. Thus, the optimum blade was corrected by slightly increasing the maximum thickness parameter of the hub section. In terms of a shape post-optimization, the blade leading edge was modified from circular to elliptical with a radius value of 1 mm (thus still satisfying the radius constraint), which was proven to decrease $Ploss$.

In Fig. 18, the final optimum blade (in purple) is compared with the baseline one (in grey). The plot is focused at the trailing edge area, where the biggest perturbations have occurred. The weighted objective functions for the optimum blade are $Ploss = 7.91\%$ and $\alpha_E^2 = 0.85 \text{ deg}^2$.

Figure 19 shows the DP axial whirl angle distribution at the outlet of the CFD domain for both baseline (left) and optimum (right) blades. It is clear that the optimum blade achieves a flow angle deviation from the axial direction close to zero.

In the following subsection, the aim is to improve the $Ploss$ objective of this blade, without significantly compromising the α_E^2 objective.

B. Constrained Optimization

At this point, only $Ploss$ is considered as objective function, whereas α_E^2 is treated as an equality constraint. The same optimization workflow that was previously presented is also used here and only the steepest descent

Figure 19. Exit whirl angle distribution for baseline (left) and optimum (right) blade.

Figure 18. 3D shape of baseline (grey) and optimum (purple) blade.

optimizer is modified. The new optimizer reads in both gradients and it projects the $Ploss$ gradient onto the plane which is orthogonal to the α_E^2 gradient. This removes all the components that would lead to a violation of the angle constraint and results in a feasible direction, tangent to the constraint. Of course, this is only a first-order approximation and, for non-linear constraints, steps normal to the constraint direction need to be added to recover feasibility. When the projection vector is found, the optimizer uses this as the gradient and perturbs the design vector using a relatively small η value. For direct control of the perturbation step-size, the line-search approach is not employed here.

This process started from the current optimum blade and it was terminated after 4 steps. In Fig. 20, the resulting non-dominated solutions (in blue) are plotted in objective space. They correspond to Pareto-like solutions, although it is not claimed that they sit on the actual Pareto-front. The horizontal axis depicts the relative difference (in %) between the current $Ploss$ and that of the baseline blade. The vertical axis shows the RMS exit whirl angle (i.e. the square root of α_E^2). The baseline point (in orange), the previous optimization output (in black) and the conventional optimization solutions (in green) are also included in this plot.

Figure 20. Different optimum solutions plotted in objective space. The blue arrows illustrate the steps of the constrained optimization process.

All the non-dominated blades satisfy the manufacturing constraints and have a smooth elliptical leading edge. The blade with minimum $Ploss$ is of particular interest and the weighted objective functions for this blade are $Ploss = 7.63\%$ and $\alpha_E^2 = 1.71 \text{ deg}^2$. In Fig. 21, this $minPloss$ blade (in blue) is compared with the baseline one (in grey). It is shown that the suction side has been perturbed in such a way that the existing separation areas are reduced. This is also illustrated in Fig. 22, where the DP total pressure distribution at an axial cross-section just behind the trailing edge is plotted for both baseline (left) and $minPloss$ (right) blades.

Figure 21. 3D shape of baseline (grey) and *minPloss* optimum (blue) blade.

Figure 22. Total pressure distribution for baseline (left) and *minPloss* optimum (right) blade.

The conventional optimization solutions are not part of the non-dominated set and possible reasons for that are discussed in the following and last section.

VII. Conclusions

This paper presents the work which has been conducted in an industrial environment for the optimization of the TU Berlin TurboLab Stator test case. The optimization is performed using both gradient-free and gradient-based automated workflows, which result in a Pareto-like set of blades with much better performance than the baseline blade. Moreover, all the produced blades satisfy the manufacturing constraints and are already available in CAD (STEP) format.

The three-step conventional gradient-free optimization solutions were dominated by the adjoint-driven blades, which can be attributed to the richer design space of the gradient-based optimization. The conventional approach used 2D CFD for optimizing the blade sections individually (thus neglecting the 3D phenomena that occur) and the stacking line was determined by the AMGA optimization which used only 4 design parameters. As a result, the conventional Pareto-front consists of blades with highly decreased flow angle deviation but increased total pressure loss. On the other hand, the adjoint-based optimization which used 192 design parameters results in blades with highly decreased flow angle deviation and also decreased total pressure loss. Regarding the total computational cost, the two approaches were similar.

The final *minPloss* blade geometry which was optimized using the SA turbulence model was also validated with the $k-\omega$ SST model, i.e. obtained similar improvements in both objectives for the two setups.

In terms of future work, a different parameterization could be used, where the B-spline control points of the blade pressure and suction sides are considered as designed parameters. This would allow a better local control over the blade surface, which could lead to a further reduction in the total pressure loss. Finally, the addition of fillets and the hub endwall contouring option will be explored.

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